

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF OUTCOMES OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH POSTOPERATIVE VENTRAL HERNIAS

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Abstract: The article presents the data of a clinical examination of 115 patients with postoperative ventral hernias, who were operated on in the surgical department of the multidisciplinary clinic of the Samarkand State Medical University for the period from 2018 to 2023. Depending on the choice of treatment tactics, the patients were divided into two groups. The first group, the comparison group, consisted of 72 (62.6%) patients who underwent open hernia repair. The second group, the main group, consisted of 43 (37.4%) patients who were initially planned for laparoscopic prosthetic hernioplasty.

Keywords: ventral hernia, alloplasty, endovideosurgery.

The relevance of research. Postoperative ventral hernias (PVH) are one of the most common pathologies that occur after surgical interventions on the abdominal cavity. They are formed as a result of violation of the integrity of the muscular-aponeurotic layer of the abdomen and are manifested by protrusion of the abdominal organs through defects in the postoperative scar [2, 4, 7].

Postoperative ventral hernias develop in 10-20% of cases after abdominal surgery. The main risk factors include:

- Wound infection: a significant factor contributing to impaired wound healing.
- Obesity: increases the load on the anterior abdominal wall.
- Chronic diseases: such as diabetes mellitus, lead to impaired tissue healing.
- Early physical activity after surgery.

Open hernioplasty has long been considered the standard treatment for POVH. However, with the development of minimally invasive technologies, laparoscopic hernioplasty has become increasingly preferred [1, 3, 5].

Laparoscopic hernioplasty involves the use of a special mesh that is fixed through small incisions. The advantages of this method include [8, 9]:

- Lower risk of infection.
- Less pain.
- Fast recovery and short hospital stay.

Despite the numerous advantages of laparoscopic hernioplasty, there are unresolved issues and problems that require further study:

1. Grid selection: The choice between absorbable and nonabsorbable materials remains a controversial issue. There is no definitive data on which grid is better in the long run.
2. Risk of relapse: One of the main issues is the high risk of relapse of POVH. Although laparoscopy reduces this risk, relapses still occur, especially in patients with large hernias or risk factors such as obesity.
3. Technical difficulties: Performing laparoscopic hernioplasty requires a highly qualified surgeon. Mistakes when installing the mesh or fixing it can lead to complications or recurrence of the hernia.
4. Study of long-term outcomes: At the moment, there is insufficient data on long-term results of laparoscopic hernioplasty. Large multicenter studies are needed to evaluate the effectiveness of this method 5-10 years after surgery [6, 10].

Thus, laparoscopic hernioplasty represents a significant step forward in the treatment of postoperative ventral hernias. However, questions related to the choice of materials, the technique of performing the operation, and long-term results remain open. Further research and technology development will help improve patient outcomes and minimize the risks associated with this type of surgery.

Purpose of the study. Improving the results of surgical treatment of patients with postoperative ventral abdominal hernias.

Material and methods of research. The study is based on a clinical examination of 115 patients with POVH who were operated on in the surgical department of the multidisciplinary clinic of Samarkand State Medical University during the period from 2018-2023. All patients were operated on as planned. Depending on the choice of treatment tactics, the patients were divided into two groups. The first group, the comparison group, consisted of 72 (62.6%) patients who underwent open herniation. The second group, the main group consisted of 43 (37.4%) patients who were scheduled for laparoscopic prosthetic hernioplasty.

The patients were divided by gender and age. The most important factors determining surgical tactics are the location of the hernia, the size of the defect, and the presence of relapses in the anamnesis. According to the classification, Chervel J. P. and Rath A.M. (1999), 82 (71.3,3%) patients had small (${}_1W_1$) and medium (${}_2W_2$) hernias. $\forall$ 33 (28.7%) patients had large hernias (${}_3-W_3-W_4$). The distribution of patients according to the location of the hernia, the size of the defect and the cause of occurrence is shown in Table 1.

The vast majority of 82 (71.3,3%) patients had supra-umbilical (M_1) and peri-umbilical (M_2) hernias. The smallest number of patients was with lateral (L) 12 (10.4%) ventral hernias. Of the 115 patients, 48 (41.7%) had a first relapse, 56 (48.7%) had a second relapse, and 11 (9.6%) had a third relapse of ventral hernia.

Table 1. Distribution of patients according to the classification of Chervel J. P. and Rath A.M.M.

Attributes			Comparison group (n=72)		The basics. group (n=43)		Total (n=115)		
			abs.	%	abs.	%	abs.	%	
S	M	M ₁	nadporozhye	25	35,7	13	30,2	38	33,0
		M ₂	umbilical	28	of 38.9	16	37,2	44	38,3
		M ₃	Podporozhye	12	16,7	8	18,6	20	of 17.4
		M ₄	suprapubic	1	1,4	0	0,0	1	0,9
	L	L ₁	subcostal	3	4,2	3	6,9	6	5,2
		L ₂	cross	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0
		L ₃	iliac	3	4,2	3	6,9	6	5,2
		L ₄	lumbar	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0
	ML	combined	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	

W	W ₁	5 cm	7	9,7	10	23,2	17	14,8
	W ₂	from 6 to 10 cm	34	47,2	31	72,1	65	of 56.5
	W ₃	11 to 15 cm	22	30,5	2	4,6	24	of 20.9
	W ₄	15 cm	9	12,5	0	0,0	9	7,8
R	R ₁	first relapse	18	25,0	30	69,8	48	41,7
	R ₂	the second	46	63,9	10	23,2	56	48,7
	R ₃	third	8	11,1	3	6,9	11	9,6

Laparoscopic hernioalloplasty of POVG consisted of the following stages:

At the first stage, a pneumoperitoneum was applied, for this purpose a Veresh needle was usually used and inserted into the classic Tracing points. But if the hernia was located in the projection of Tracing points, then the pneumoperitoneum in this case was applied under the control of intraoperative ultrasound (IOUSI). The Veresh needle was inserted, where there were no intestinal loops that were soldered to the anterior abdominal wall (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Stage of applying pneumoperitoneum through a minilaparotomy incision

At the second stage, for a better view and manipulation, the laparoscope and working trocars were inserted at a sufficient distance from the aponeurotic edge of the hernia gate, since the endoprosthesis should be located at a distance of 4-5 cm from the edge of the hernia gate (Fig. 2).

2. Installation of trocars at a sufficient distance from the aponeurotic edge of the hernial gate

After installing the trocars, the abdominal cavity and the state of the organs were visualized at the third stage. Adhesions in the abdominal cavity were dissected and places for fixation and placement of the endoprosthesis were examined (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Dissection of adhesions

At the fourth stage, the prosthesis was prepared by applying it to the anterior abdominal wall, and at the same time the internal surface of the abdominal wall was examined through a laparoscope, measuring the prosthesis so that it extended 4-5 cm beyond the edges of the hernial gate (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. View of a mesh polypropylene implant whose perimeter dimensions are 5 cm larger than the size of the hernial defect

At the fifth stage, the prosthesis was fixed with through sutures to the aponeurosis using U-shaped sutures previously applied to the endoprosthesis with a special Endo Close needle modified by us Close(Fig. 5).

Figure 5. The stage of endoprosthesis fixation to aponeurosis

In order to prevent early adhesive intestinal obstruction and infiltrate of the abdominal cavity, the endoprosthesis was isolated from the abdominal cavity by the parietal peritoneum (Fig..

6. Isolation of the endoprosthesis from the abdominal cavity by the parietal peritoneum

Research results. Analysis of the obtained data showed that patients of the main group who underwent laparoscopic prosthetic hernioplasty showed better performance in the postoperative period compared to patients of the comparison group.

The average duration of surgery in the main group was 75 ± 15 minutes, while in the comparison group it was 105 ± 20 minutes. This is due to the less traumatic nature of the laparoscopic method and the higher accuracy of performing manipulations (Fig. 7).

Figure 7. Comparative indicators of operation duration (min) depending on the attempted access

In patients of the main group, the level of pain on the first day after surgery was significantly lower than in patients of the comparison group, which is confirmed by the use of lower doses of analgesics.

The time spent in hospital after surgery in patients of the main group averaged 3.5 ± 1.2 days, while in patients of comparison groups, this indicator was 7.4 ± 2.1 days. Faster recovery allowed patients in the main group to return to normal activity earlier.

The main group had a lower number of postoperative complications. In particular, 2 (4.6%) patients of the main group had minor seromas that were successfully resolved by conservative methods. In the comparison group, complications such as wound infection and hernia recurrence were noted in 11 (15.3,3%) patients (Table 2).

Table 2. Results of surgical treatment of patients with POVH

Indicators	Comparison group (n=72)	Main group (n=43)
Operation duration (min)	105±20	75±15
Hospital stay (day)	7.4±2.1	3.5±1.2
Seroma (%)	8.3	4.6
Wound suppuration (%)	6.9	-
Hernia recurrence (%)	5.5	-

Conclusion. The study confirmed the high effectiveness of laparoscopic prosthetic hernioplasty in the treatment of postoperative ventral hernias. Patients who underwent laparoscopic surgery had better clinical outcomes, including a shorter rehabilitation period, lower pain intensity, and a lower risk of postoperative complications. The data obtained indicate the need for further implementation of laparoscopic hernioplasty in clinical practice and its active use to improve the quality of treatment of patients with ventral hernias.

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